

FACTORS OF FORMATION OF GENDER EQUALITY THINKING IN STUDENTS

Allayarova Noila Yaxshinor qizi

Named after Islam Karimov

Tashkent State Technical University

Teacher of the Foreign Languages Department:

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Abstract: the issue of the interrelationship of mental thinking with ideas as a unique form of thinking is very complex and multifaceted, ideas occupy an important place in human life and in the development of society, the history of humanity consists of the history of ideas, any nation and people, any the social system and the state are dedicated to living on the basis of certain principles and values

Key words : gender studies, gender equality , thinking, women's rights , legal standards , stereotype , pedagogical experiment , socio-political , national-spiritual, psychological and pedagogical , national independence,

Introduction.

Based on the analysis of research carried out so far and the establishment of a pedagogical experiment in higher education institutions, we found it necessary to classify the factors of the formation of gender equality thinking in students into the following four groups: social-political, national-spiritual, psychological and pedagogical.

When thinking about the socio-political factors of the formation of gender equality thinking among students, it is certainly permissible to dwell on the issues of national independence and development strategy, the works of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the national idea and political socialization.

Development strategy for the further development of new Uzbekistan is a very perfect and universal strategic doctrine based on deeply thought ideas and theories for our nation to be free and prosperous. It is recognized around the world as it fully embodies the entire socio-political activity, leadership ability, historical, economic, cultural-educational, ideological-theoretical, philosophical-practical worldviews, all efforts of our President.

Materials

The activities in all areas implemented and increased within the framework of the Development Strategy at the initiative and calls of the President have their own specific and general methodological scientific-theoretical bases, principles and priorities, concepts and criteria.

As a specific form of thinking, the question of the relationship between mental thinking and the idea is very complex and multifaceted. Ideas play an important role in human life and in the development of society. In this sense, it can be said that the history of mankind consists of the history of ideas. Any nation and people, any social system and state lives on the basis of certain principles and values. He acts in pursuit of his own interests, goals, dreams and aspirations. In the implementation of important reforms and changes in the life of a person and society, certain ideas guide human activity and occupy a special place. The acceleration or deceleration of the development of the society in different periods, high development and

serious crises, the occurrence of positive or negative situations in the life of the society, which ideas are dominant in the society, whether they are based on spiritual and moral foundations, and which social strata serve their interests depend in many ways.

Methods

Human mind, intelligence, thinking creates different thoughts, views, ideas and doctrines during perception of reality. Therefore, ideas are the product of human thinking. But any thought, view, reflection, or otherwise point of view created by thought cannot be an idea. Based on the results of philosophical thinking, general conclusions have been reached today about the essence and epistemological status of the idea: the idea is one of the unique forms of knowledge of the world that is formed under the influence of reality and life. It expresses specific goals of an individual, society, social group, party, etc., unites, organizes, motivates and mobilizes them in this way.

The national idea is an idea that awakens the national consciousness, signifies the identity of the nation, gives a "face" to the identity, mentality, and forms the feelings of national spirit, pride, pride, faith and responsibility; the idea that embodies the understanding of the nation's past, present and future, represents its basic interests and goals as an ethno-social unit, and serves its development is called a national idea; national idea - a set of good ideas leading the people of the country forward; the idea of national independence is a moral criterion that mobilizes every compatriot and member of our entire society to fulfill their duties and responsibilities to the Motherland; national idea - expresses the nation's highest ideal (object), long-term goals, dreams, will, so to speak, its unique historical "claim" in a general form. It expresses the essence of the society we are striving for and building in two words in a simple and understandable way.

The idea, as a product of human thought, is nourished by the national-cultural heritage, relies on universal human values, and is found in the process of studying and analyzing social and spiritual life and the surrounding world. All forms of social consciousness create, rely on and develop certain ideas in the fields of science, philosophy, religion, art and fiction, ethics, politics, and law.

As with any phenomenon, the development of gender thinking is naturally subject to constant change and development. It can be seen that various factors have their own influence and role. Among them, the political factor is of particular importance. After all, "the life of every society revolves around the axis of the current policy. Therefore, this influence can have a strong positive or negative content, depending on the nature of the policy being pursued."

Results

The political factor is manifested as the cause of the processes taking place on the political front in the life of the society, and can have a positive or negative effect, hinder, limit or, on the contrary, act as an incentive.

Our society present development headache _ a person of factor , person socio-political of activity legal respectively grow up going with separate stands _ This for nothing not because _ all social relationships from the total consists of has been of the person creative activities develop , to work put brand new ways and opportunities looking for without finding , social work release efficiency by increasing it won't be .

Discussion

Humanity of development different in the head social life for the most important from tasks one - of the person political socialization process done is to increase . Otherwise by doing in other words , of a person social his life _ political in processes participation reach and is available political system with mutually in relation to be , ideology and legislation , moral views and values system mastering to go and socio-political in actions , the public in their work participation reach and attraction to be done in the process done increased goes _ Own in turn , political to life step put new generation socialization , society in his life political processes continuity and political of development succession provides .

Conclusion

This and the state with citizens between mutually relationships proportionality to the achievement possibility gives and is available of the system stable development guarantees . " Political socialization - of the individual political in the system is available political faith , views , orientations , political values and norms appropriation process " .

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